

TOPIC MODELING IN SOCIAL SCIENCE - WHAT IT IS AND HOW TO USE IT

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Students in the Digital Society Master Program of the JKU during the summer term of 2023

Release via: Zenodo [\[https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8084918\]](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8084918)

Youtube [\[https://youtu.be/xgtYvuVcVuo\]](https://youtu.be/xgtYvuVcVuo)

Release date: [11/09/23]

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The following OER was created for the course:

231.013 Methoden der empirischen Sozialforschung (in) der digitalen Gesellschaft

Questions regarding the assessment of the OER should be forwarded to Mag. Dr. Dimitri Prandner (Dimitri.Prandner@jku.at)

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July 2023

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Open Educational Research Project

SE Methods of empirical social research (in) the digital society
Digital Society M.Sc.

Abstract

In this OER we would like to offer an overview of topic modeling as a method for social scientist with no expert knowledge in the field of computational social sciences.

Following general information on the scientific background and technical information on the method we would like to answer the following questions: How can social scientists use topic modeling? What can and cannot the method achieve? What are the limitations? We discuss the research question of 'Which topics occur related to artificial intelligence in journal articles across STEM disciplines and social sciences?' as an example. Based on this, we explain how a research process entailing the use of a topic model could be structured and what the potentials and challenges of applying the method are. In the last part of the OER we discuss how topic modeling can be part of a mixed methods research design, further developing our example.

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Introduction

Digitalization has become ubiquitous in society, influencing both human behavior and scientific research. Regarding the former, there have been notable changes, such as the emergence of new communication channels like social media, blogs, and vast digital databases that store and transmit substantial amounts of information. These changes have given rise to a variety of digital data formats. As for the latter, scientific research has also undergone transformations, leading to the exploration of new research fields and the adoption of novel research questions and methods (Zamith & Lewis, 2015). One such new research stream is computational social science (CSS) entailing new ways of epistemology and working with digital or digitized research data as well as computational methods.

In the social sciences, new research methods often build upon existing ones instead of being developed entirely from scratch. One such method emerged within the computational social science is topic modeling. It is an automated text analysis technique that integrates the principles of traditional content analysis. Topic modeling is particularly advantageous when applied to large text corpora that would be impractical to analyze manually, offering new opportunities for scholars (Chen et al., 2023).

However, these new possibilities also come with challenges. Issues such as data quality, the validity and reliability of results (Kitchin, 2014; Lazer et al., 2020), and the interdisciplinary nature of computational social sciences (CSS) - requiring competences in both social sciences and computational sciences - have led many scientists to hesitate and be skeptical about adopting new automated methods for analyzing novel types of data.

In light of these concerns, this article aims to provide an overview of topic modeling as a research method for social scientists within the context of an open educational research (OER) project. It begins by presenting background information on computational social sciences and addressing epistemological considerations. The main focus is then directed towards topic modeling. We present information on what topic modeling is, its purpose, and the ongoing scientific debates surrounding it. Additionally, we outline how scholars in the social sciences can effectively utilize this research method.

To illustrate the practical application of topic modeling, we discuss a specific research question as an example: "Which topics are prevalent in journal articles across STEM disciplines and social

sciences concerning artificial intelligence?" Building upon this example, we explain how a research process involving the use of a topic model could be structured. This includes steps such as data collection, text preparation, analysis, and validation. Throughout this process, we highlight both the potentials and challenges associated with applying the topic modeling method.

In the final section of the OER, we explore how topic modeling can be integrated into a mixed methods research design, further expanding upon our earlier example, and demonstrating its versatility and adaptability in different research contexts.

Methodological Background

Computational Social Science

Social-technical changes have not only impacted society and economics, but also science and academic institutions. Consequently, digital technologies, virtual spaces, and digital data have given rise to new research fields, such as human-computer interaction or online communication, and have introduced new research approaches for scholars (Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018). Among these emerging research streams is computational social science (CSS), which scholars have employed increasingly since 2012 (Edelmann et al., 2020). It has developed from both social science as well as STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) areas of expertise. In the social sciences, CSS has involved computational simulations of human behavior for theoretical advancement, while STEM disciplines have encompassed any research that utilizes large digital datasets (Edelmann et al., 2020).

Based on these separate premises, Edelmann et al. (2020) define CSS as “an interdisciplinary field that advances theories of human behavior by applying computational techniques to large datasets from social media sites, the Internet, or other digitized archives such as administrative records” (p. 2).

This definition implies certain assumptions. Firstly, CSS requires expertise in social science as well as computational science in order to apply computational methods and interpret the results appropriately and validly (Lazer et al., 2020). Secondly, CSS goes beyond simply using computers for research; it involves the integration of computational technologies like algorithms in data analysis to test existing sociological theories or develop new ones (Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018).

Lastly, CSS focuses on the analysis of large digital or digitized datasets that cannot be effectively analyzed by humans alone (Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018).

Computational social scientists utilize various methods and measurement, including for instance (partly) automated content analysis, text mining analysis or network modeling, which indicates new kinds of data as well as new processing and analyzing technologies and tools that come with both new opportunities and new challenges (Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018). These methods are applied in many research fields, with communication science, sociology and political science being the most active ones within the social sciences (Edelmann et al., 2020).

What is Computational Social Science?

... "an interdisciplinary field that advances theories of human behavior by applying computational techniques to large datasets from social media sites, the Internet, or other digitized archives such as administrative records."

The large amounts of data are mainly referred to as digital traces or big data characterized by their substantial volume, variety, and velocity (Salganik, 2018). Kitchin (2014) refines the definition by adding the exhaustive, indexical, flexible, and relational dimensions that big data inherit. Big data can imply administrative data, data from digital devices, social media data, or any other quantitative data generated digitally or digitized and archived (Kitchin 2014; Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018).

By using computational methods, researchers are able to examine data about human behavior in a non-reactive way without researchers actively intervening in human behavior (Van Atteveldt & Peng, 2018). Additionally, big data is produced continually and can be tracked in real-time, enabling researchers to study unprecedented events or conduct large longitudinal comparative studies (Kitchin, 2014).

However, researchers face numerous challenges when applying computational methods and working with big data which are mostly tied to the context of the data's origin. Scientists have to come to terms with messiness and uncertainty (Kitchin, 2014). Digital trace data are often produced by commercial platforms, whose aim is not to record a representative image of their user's lives, but who collect data for their specific, commercial purposes. What is more, the share of their collected data that they make available to research is even more biased, as the platforms

deliberately chose what information to make public according to their interests (Törnberg & Törnberg). Consequently, big data is often incomplete or unrepresentative and lacks information about participants and behavior, or information necessary for data operationalization (Salganik, 2020). Moreover, big data is originally not created for scientific research, resulting in partial inaccessibility due to private ownership or privacy regulations (Törnberg & Törnberg, 2018). Additionally, big data systems change, hindering comparative measurements or reliability checks over time (Salganik, 2020).

Another issue relates to algorithms. On one hand, online behavior is often influenced by algorithms which can introduce potential biases and mislead the interpretation of results (Törnberg & Törnberg, 2018). On the other hand, researchers using algorithms as computational method should be aware that algorithms often struggle to adequately capture meaning and context (Kitchin, 2014).

These opportunities and difficulties should be considered also in regard to the process of knowledge production.

Epistemological Implications of Automated Content Analysis

The above-mentioned opportunities and challenges within CSS and computational methods, as well as the use of big data, have implications regarding knowledge production. Kitchin (2014) explores two streams of new epistemological approaches in relation to digital data: 1) a new era of empiricism, 2) a new mode of data-driven science.

Advocates of the new era of empiricism argue that scientific methods and theories have become redundant. Due to the accessibility of big datasets, analyzing them can reveal inferences and correlations which are sufficient results without the need for additional explanation. Instead, the ability to predict is seen as more important than deeper examination, which makes this approach mostly interesting for marketing and retail fields in commercial sectors, since here, the need for high standards of validity and reliability checks are less urgent than in research. Additionally, big data is seen as unaffected by human biases or framing and, as it speaks for itself, can be interpreted by anyone regardless of their level of expertise. These assumptions can be highly problematic, because this position opposes deductive research methods which imply a priori theories or theoretically derived hypothesis (Kitchin, 2014). Consequently, the empiricist approach has

frequently been criticized for various reasons that counteract the aforementioned assumptions arguing that big data is neither complete and representative, nor neutral and free from human biases (Kitchin, 2014; Törnberg & Törnberg, 2018). This highlights the need for competencies to interpret results correctly.

Supporters of the new mode of data-driven science argue for a combination of inductive, abductive as well as deductive research methods. Thereby, theoretical assumptions underlie the data analyzing process, and the findings generate insights that constitute prerequisites for building new hypothesis and test them deductively. Hence, the abductive process, as a mode of logical inference, considers existing theories as starting point for data analysis as well as new theory building as the endpoint from the findings from the data (Kitchin, 2014).

Kitchin (2014) argues for the latter epistemological approach, but adds some crucial considerations which highlights the need for contextualization and reflection when working with big data:

In other words, it is possible to think of new epistemologies that do not dismiss or reject Big Data analytics, but rather employ the methodological approach of data-driven science within a different epistemological framing that enables social scientists to draw valuable insights from Big Data that are situated and reflexive.

When working with natural language (text as data) and applying automated text analysis, which is part of CSS, Baranowski (2022) distinguishes between deductive and inductive methods of automated text analysis. The deductive approach involves manual categorization of data by computational social scientists before analysis. This process requires time and knowledge of the data's essence and characteristics (Quinn et al., 2010). An example of a deductive method is Supervised Learning, where researchers label (categorize) training data, and the algorithm learns patterns from this data to analyze new data in subsequent steps (Quinn et al., 2010). On the other hand, inductive methods of natural language processing are useful when researchers have limited knowledge about the substance of the texts. Through an Unsupervised Learning process, the algorithm discovers patterns in unlabeled documents (Baranowski, 2022; Quinn et al., 2010). One example of this is the Topic Model, which is the focus of this article.

Considering the insights of Kitchin (2014), Baranowski (2022), and Quinn et al. (2010), it is crucial to acknowledge the significance of the epistemological dimension throughout the entire research process. Consequently, knowledge production is contingent upon various decisions made during

the research design, such as formulating the research question and selecting the appropriate data and metadata. Simultaneously, epistemology impacts multiple steps of the research process like data collection and preprocessing (source). This extends to the interpretation of the essence of topics within the Topic Model. The term "topic" can be used differently in various studies, encompassing themes, issues, frames, or voices, depending on the chosen parameters (Jacobi et al., 2016). This aligns with Kitchin's (2014) call to contextualize and critically analyze the data. Furthermore, as previously mentioned, the substance of the texts is also significant. For instance, speeches or newspapers exhibit distinct writing and speaking styles.

Topic Modeling

After this brief introduction to the background of Topic Modeling and the field of computational social science we will get to the core of the matter of this OER in following part, explaining what Topic Modeling is, what kinds of Topic Models there are and how they work. Topic Modeling (TM) is an unsupervised method for automatic analysis of text. By applying a topic model, computational social scientists aim to discover latent topics that occur in a certain text corpus (Chen et al., 2023). To this end, TM-algorithms are statistically analyzing words of the text corpus regarding the themes the texts incorporate, how those themes change over time and which correlations occur between them (Blei, 2012). A major benefit of topic modeling is that the method

What is Topic Model?

Topic Modeling (TM) is an unsupervised method for automatic analysis of text. By applying a topic model, computational social scientists aim to discover latent topics that occur in a certain text corpus.

can be utilized to investigate large data sets such as media archives, social media posts or academic databases that would not be processible manually due to their vast volumes.

Before being analyzed by means of a topic model, text corpuses need to be pre-processed to be comprehensible and processable to the model. Researchers need to transform it into a matrix and, depending on the topic model, perform pre-processing steps such as removing of so-called stopwords or numbers (Chen et al., 2023). Topic Models output topics,

which are groups of words that are more likely to occur together than others as well as topic proportions of each topic per document (Chen et al., 2023).

There are different types of Topic Model, the most widely used being LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation). In the following section, we aim to give a brief overview of exemplary common Topic Models, explaining their basic functionalities, how they work and how they differ.

LDA – Latent Dirichlet Allocation

LDA models are based on a generative model, that means that they employ an underlying assumption about how the data was generated, or in the case of text analysis, how the author would choose the words they put in the text (Van Atteveldt et al., 2022). The model implies an abstract process of writing texts based on the topics that they should entail. The Model than ‘reverses the process’ and thereby can deduce the entailed topics (Van Atteveldt et al., 2022).

We try to make this a little bit clearer by the following example: In our abstract process, the author is first deciding how long the text should be and what it should be about. Therefore, they assign topics and respective shares of the text: The text should be 60% about cats and 40% about dogs. If the text should be 1000 words long, 600 random words will thus be about cats, and 400 random words will be about dogs. The author than randomly chooses 600 words associated with the topic cats and 400 words associated with dogs and puts them into the document.

Presuming this process, the LDA model can infer that the document is probably about cats and dogs, and even suggest the proportion of the two topics.

For applying a LDA model to a dataset, it is essential that the contained texts are pre-processed by removing word-order, document-order, stop words, numbers, etc. (Albanese, 2022).

The pre-processed documents are then computed: To be able to define which words belong to which topics, LDA uses topic vectors (Hulstaert, 2017). These are calculated from occurrences of words in each document. The counts of every word of the entire vocabulary of the text corpus are being depicted in a vector for each document. This way, the model can infer that certain words often occur together whereas other words are hardly used in proximity, and therefore deduct topics (Hulstaert, 2017).

To summarize: LDA topic models infer a hidden structure of the documents (the topics and their probability) from the observed variables (the words of the document) (Blei, 2012) by transforming the words and documents into mathematical vectors (Hulstaert, 2017).

LDA models decide on topics based on the collectivity of words, they can also take into account, that some words might have different meanings in different contexts (Van Atteveldt et al., 2022). The word nail, for example, might refer to biology as well as to woodwork, depending on the other words in the document.

Additional to the generative model, LDA relies on further assumptions, one which is the ‘bag of words’ assumptions. It implies that the order of words in the document does not matter (Blei, 2012). Equally irrelevant to the LDA-model is the order of the documents. There have, however, emerged several extensions of LDA that relax these assumptions and take, for example, the order of documents into account (Blei, 2012).

LDA models make another assumption: The number of topics is known. This can be achieved by defining a certain number of topics before conducting the model. The number can be changed in an iterative process to find the configuration that best explain the text corpus (Hulstaert, 2017). As opposed to clustering algorithms, LDA models do not assume that every document is associated just with one topic, but rather that various topics can be found in one document, with different proportions assigned to them. This is called a mixed-membership model (Grimmer et al., 2022) and makes LDA approaches especially suitable for research questions concerned with finding several topics in longer texts. LDA models can be used for small as well as large datasets (Albanese, 2022).

Word Embedding Based Models - Top2vec & BERTopic

As LDA Models do not always produce entirely satisfying outcomes for all kinds of texts (Egger & Yu, 2022), other kinds of topic models have been developed. Especially the fact that LDA models do not take the semantic relationship between words into account lead to the development of models that rely on word and document embeddings. Following, we briefly describe two popular examples for this kind of topic model:

Top2vec is a topic modeling algorithm that uses word embeddings and document embeddings that are assigning vectors to words and documents. Vectorization allows for computing the semantic proximity and locating words and documents in a high dimensional space. For example, ‘apple’ and ‘pear’ are located closer to each other than ‘apple’ and ‘typewriter’. After reducing the

dimensionality, Top2Vec is clustering similar documents into topics. The centroid of a cluster is defined as the topic vector. The word vectors closest to the topic vector result in the description of the topic (Egger & Yu, 2022).

BERTopic has been developed based on Top2Vec and other topic models using word and document embeddings (Grootendorst, 2022). It objects the assumption that words closest to a centroid topic vector best represent a topic. Thus, it avoids a centroid approach and instead applies a class-based version of TF-IDF (Grootendorst, 2022). TF-IDF is short for term frequency – inverse document frequency. The TF-IDF is a value assigned to a term and depicts how significant a certain term is to a certain document by calculating how often the term appears in a document and offsetting this value with how many documents in the whole collection or corpus contain the word.

Both algorithms, Top2Vec and BERTopic, do not assign multiple topics to documents. Instead, each document is tied to one topic. As opposed to working with LDA models, researchers do not need to define the number of topics beforehand, but the models deliver an estimation of found topics. As these sometimes contain rather many results, Top2Vec as well as BERTopic offer the possibility to reduce the amount of topics (Egger & Yu, 2022).

While often generating more meaningful and coherent topics, Top2Vec and BERTopic also show limitations: as opposed to LDA, they produce a large number of outliers (Albanese, 2022). These are elements that cannot be assigned to a certain topic by the model, BERTopic will summarize them in a topic with the count -1 which should always be discounted by the researcher (Egger & Yu, 2022). What is more, BERTopic and Top2Vec tend to work better on large datasets of short texts, such as social media posts or headlines (Albanese, 2022).

What Can We Do With Topic Modeling?

The aforementioned overview of different topic model methods is highly relevant when considering how researchers can utilize topic modeling within the social sciences. It encompasses issues related to methodology, research fields as well as the types of research questions that can

be explored using topic models. Since topic modeling is a relatively new research approach, there is currently no standardized way for conducting it (Chen et al. 2023).

By providing a systematic review of topic modeling, Chen et al. (2023) present a framework that includes three normative arguments regarding theory building and testing. Firstly, they emphasize the importance of appropriate conceptualization which is grounded in theory and fits the context of research. In the field of computational social science and automated content analysis methods such as topic modeling, theory can involve patterns and frameworks derived from earlier research that illustrate the production, usage, and influences on digital data (Patty & Penn, 2014). It can also incorporate macro-level theories from online communication studies (Waldherr et al., 2021).

In previous research projects, topic modeling has primarily been used in a descriptive manner, focusing on data-driven outcomes and neglecting the relevance of connecting data analysis procedures to theory. This approach limits the potential of topic modeling to detect structures or meanings within textual data and large corpora and which was not possible through manual coding alone (Chen et al., 2023).

The second normative argument highlights the importance of working with hypotheses. This can be achieved deductively by testing existing hypotheses or inductively by generating new hypotheses for future research.

The third normative argument involves choosing the appropriate topic model, which depends on the research context and the text data to be analyzed. The selection of the right model should consider the necessary functionalities of the topic model, aiding in the decision-making process (Chen et al., 2023). The previous chapter provides a list of topic models, their possibilities, limitations, and their applicability. Applying topic modeling as a research method facilitates gaining initial insights into the content of large amounts of textual data, as it "transforms a large sample of text into a much smaller set of topics" (Chen et al., 2023, p. 112). However, researchers need to exercise caution to avoid overusing topic modeling and should also consider alternative methods for content analysis.

Existing research incorporating topic modeling within the research design demonstrates its broad application across various types of text data and research questions. Text data sources range from digital-born data such as social media posts to digitized and digitally archived data such as speeches or online newspaper articles, as well as scientific journal articles in digital format, all within the

context of large data sets. In the systematic literature reviews conducted by Chen et al. (2023), they found that tweets, news reports, and Facebook posts were the most commonly used text data when applying topic modeling methods.

Regarding research questions, scholars have various opportunities. As mentioned earlier, TM can be used to describe the content of textual data. Additionally, it enables comparative research, including the examination of topics and their changes over time, the comparison of topics across different types of text data, or the exploration of topics within different text corpora of the same type of data, among others (Chen et al, 2023).

Giving an Example

Based on a hypothetical research question, we provide one exemplary use case of topic modeling to demonstrate each step of the procedure and considerations when applying topic model.

Research Question

We examine the use of topic modeling by asking the following research question:

Which topics occur related to artificial intelligence in journal articles across STEM disciplines and social sciences?

As interdisciplinary research gains popularity, it becomes intriguing to explore the topics that arise within individual disciplines. This exploration allows us to identify both similarities and differences, revealing potential areas of common ground for interdisciplinary research between social sciences and STEM disciplines, creating new potential research fields even such as CSS.

This research question aims to compare how scientists from different disciplines discuss artificial intelligence, identify the topics they cover, and explore similarities or differences. The research process is primarily descriptive, serving as a starting point for studying scientific communication about artificial intelligence in different fields. Alternative research processes, such as inductive or abductive, are also possible but require more theoretical knowledge to expand methodological assumptions.

Text Data: Journal Articles

Journal articles are utilized as the text data for this research, offering both advantages and challenges. The benefits stem from the accuracy of the meta data of journal articles which is also due to the high degree of standardization. For example, most articles include an abstract, publication date, and information about the publishing journal (Baranowski, 2022). This standardization is particularly true for articles in English, which serves as a common language in most research fields.

However, there are also obstacles we have to consider when working with journal articles as research data. Access to articles is often limited by financial resources or institutional membership, as not all papers are openly available. Another challenge relates to the dataset's logic and historical dimension. Some articles are not available in a digital format suitable for computational analysis, either because they are only scanned or not digitized at all. Hence, the dataset is incomplete. This limitation becomes particularly relevant when examining topic changes over time and including data from older articles, approximately 15 years or older.

Data collection involves selecting a suitable database for examining academic papers in the relevant disciplines. In this hypothetical case, data is collected from the online database Scopus, covering the period from 2019 to the present. The time frame can be adjusted depending on the number of filtered articles. For example, if the volume of articles is too large for the model to process, the time frame can be reduced. The keyword search focuses on "artificial intelligence," filtering articles that contain this term in the title, abstract, and keyword list. Additionally, only English-language articles are included. The disciplines are filtered through the subject area selection button on Scopus.

Model: LDA Topic Model

The LDA topic model is selected for our research question based on several assumptions derived from the abovementioned remarks. LDA is suitable for analyzing larger text, as journal articles are, and allows for multiple topics per document which is interesting to examine in this case (Grimmer et al., 2022). We assume that the word order in the text is not relevant for the research question, and we can therefore also facilitate the text by applying certain preprocessing steps outlined by Denny and Spirling (2018). These pre-processing steps must be appropriately tailored to the

research field and question. It is important to note that the order in which these steps are applied can influence the analysis, findings, and results.

Consequently, we remove punctuation and numbers and convert all words to lowercase since these factors are considered uninformative for the research question. To reduce the vocabulary and thus, streamline the automated analyzing process, stemming or lemmatizing and the removal of stopwords can be implemented. Stopwords encompass function words like “the”, “we”, or “to” and are listed in libraries, such as the NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) library, which can be imported in the topic model. Researchers can also add stopwords to the list. In this example the words “artificial” and “intelligence” can be defined as additional stopwords since artificial intelligence serve as search keyword and represent the overall theme, which should not be part of the resulting topics. Infrequently used terms can also be designated as stopwords. Furthermore, n-gram can be included which involve terms consisting of two or more words treated as one unit in the topic model. For instance, “data protection” could be defined as a 2-gram. (Denny & Springer, 2018)

Another preprocess step is the decision about the number of the topics. As already mentioned, this is an iterative process of trial and error (Namyang, 2021; Hulstaert, 2021). Existing literature in the field can provide us with insights into the expected topics.

After data collection and preprocessing, computational analysis can be conducted, followed by labelling, validation, and interpretation of topics. To label the topics, we take into account the clusters of words the topic model is presenting to us. It’s important to document all steps and adjustments. Finally, we manually code associated text and thereby validate the topics which we focus on in the next part of the article.

An overview of the procedural steps of topic modeling are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research process - LDA topic model

Validation

A crucial aspect of topic modeling is the validation of the method. The algorithms of automated text analysis tools are often a kind of black box that does not let us reconstruct the detailed path that the model took to get to the results proposes. Hence, it is critical that topic models are validated before continuing the research based on their output (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013). However crucial validation is, there is not one way that suits all topic models, but rather there are various options of validating a model. A widely used approach is the one proposed by DiMaggio et. al (2013). The authors put forward three forms of validation, comprising semantic or internal validation, statistical validation and predictive or external validation.

All three forms involve comparing the results to a validation criterion (Quinn et al., 2010). Semantic or internal validation involves manual coding of documents and comparing the results to the output of the model. Thereby, the researchers can determine whether the model is able to meaningfully discriminate between topics as well as between different uses of the same or similar term (DiMaggio, 2013). The internal validation also questions whether the topics are coherent and expectable in regard to their content.

The second form of validation, statistical validation, looks into the assumptions of the model and checks whether the output is consistent with them. This form reviews if the model is working well

statistically by employing different metrics that need to be chosen according to the topic model that is used (DiMaggio, 2013).

Thirdly, the authors suggest predictive or external validation. It entails comparing the occurrence of topics to external events. The researchers formulate hypotheses, estimating the prevalence of certain topics based on external factors and then examine whether there is a correlation between the topics and the events (DiMaggio, 2013). For example, a hypothesis could be that a topic concerned with ChatGPT is occurring often at the end of 2022 and the beginning of 2023, as the chatbot was publicly launched in November 2022. The hypothesis would then be tested by comparing the number of words or documents that are associated with this topic over time. A topic entailing ChatGPT that occurs frequently before 2022 should lead the researcher to reconsider the parameters of the algorithm.

Summing up, validating the topic model can be rather laborious and challenging. Nevertheless, it is crucial for achieving valid results that can be built on in further research. Only this way, researchers doing topic modeling can confront critics who discount the method as not valid and not suited for social sciences.

Challenges and Limitations

As we have shown in the previous chapters, topic modeling in social research can have major benefits. The method does, however, also bring about challenges and limitations that social researchers need to consider when planning their research designs. Additional to the validation of a topic model that can be intricate at times, there are three further aspects of the model that we would like to discuss here: dealing with digital data, the language bias, and the difficulties with teaching topic modeling for social sciences.

Topic Modeling and Data

The characteristics of the data we analyze by means of topic models have elaborately been described in Chapter 1. Thus, we would like to sum up the challenges that are tied to big data very briefly: big data frequently pose problems regarding their accessibility and quality (Salganik, 2017.) Digital trace data are often produced by commercial platforms, whose aim is not to record a

representative image of their user's lives, but who collect data for their specific, commercial purposes. Hence, scientists have to come to terms with messiness and uncertainty (Kitchin, 2014). What is more, the share of the collected data that platforms make available to research is even more biased, as they deliberately chose what information to make public according to their interests (Törnberg & Törnberg, 2018). It is therefore essential that social researchers take the context in which the data was born into account when applying automated text analysis such as topic models. These problems can also be transferred to different kinds of digital data, such as the journal articles from our example mentioned above: considering metadata such as author, publisher, publishing date, etc. is crucial to assess whether the dataset is biased or compromised.

Language Bias in Topic Modeling

Some major limitations of the method relate to the bias regarding languages in most topic models. Many can only work with one language, which is mostly English (Lind et al., 2019), and even though new approaches like BERTopic support up to 50 different languages (Grootendorst, 2022), the majority of the languages supported is spoken in the global north or in countries with more developed research infrastructures. Researchers are forced to use different models for different languages within one research design which can lead to problems regarding the comparability and validity of results, some research cannot be conducted at all due to a lack of an adequate topic model (Lind et al., 2019). This leads to a vast amount of data that cannot be analyzed using certain topic models, including multilingual texts or text in languages that are not supported by many models. Hence, social research employing topic modeling needs to be considered biased and is further reinforcing existing divides in global social science (Lind et al., 2019).

Difficulties in Teaching Topic Modeling for Social Sciences

Another challenging or limiting aspect in regard to topic modeling is something we experienced ourselves, taking a course on 'methods for empirical social research in the digital society'. Running a topic model requires basic programming skills if the researcher is conducting their research project on their own. It therefore needs interdisciplinary teaching, involving programming as well as social research skills.

This might discourage lecturers as well as students, and without at least a basic understanding of programming languages such as python, learning topic models can be rather challenging. However, we also found that as soon as one's interest in the method is sparked, basic programming skills can easily be self-taught using online sources.

Augmenting Topic Modeling by Applying It in a Mixed Methods Approach

Researchers in the social sciences are dealing with more and more complex questions. These are asking for multi-perspective, multidisciplinary, qualitative and quantitative methods (Kuckartz, 2014). In order to apply adequate methods to complex research problems, many social scientists have adapted mixed methods approaches, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to best answering their questions (Kuckartz, 2014). Halcomb et al. (2009) stress that mixed methods is not the mere blending of qualitative and quantitative tools but rather a methodology that entails the planned combination of concerted qualitative and quantitative methods with the objective of better outcomes and more suitable answers to the research question (Halcomb et al., 2009).

Mixed methods designs can be applied to serve different purposes for research (Kuckartz, 2014): Triangulation designs seek to validate results by achieving congruent outcomes through different methods. Designs striving for complementarity are applied to elaborate findings and improve the understanding the researchers have of their results. Further designs entail strategies to improve the methodology using the outcomes of the applied methods, or to review results from earlier studies (Kuckartz, 2014).

Summing up, mixed method designs can augment research in various ways. Especially with research questions that can only partly be answered by the application of computational methods, a mixed methods approach can be valuable to social sciences. In the following part, we want to illustrate the use of topic modeling within a mixed methods approach by giving a few examples from current research.

Eickhoff and Wienecke (2018) have diagnosed shortcomings of LDA topic modeling that they propose to resolve by embedding the method in a mixed methods design. According to the authors, topic modeling often is concomitant with a loss of contextual meaning. To avoid this, they propose a multi-step process starting with applying an LDA topic model followed by iterative

qualitative coding steps. The researchers manually coded the topics relating to the associated documents and thereby recontextualized the previously decontextualized (in the course of pre-processing steps for the topic modeling the context of the words was removed) topics. By discussing the codes within the team, they ensured inter-coder reliability. Several iterative coding cycles resulted in meaningful topics (Eickhoff & Wienecke, 2018). The approach the authors chose is a sequential approach, meaning that the methods are conducted one after the other (Kuckartz, 2014). This example shows that mixed methods designs entailing topic modeling can be used for triangulation purposes by cross validating the results, as well as for making findings more complementary.

Another possible sequential design is the one that Singer et al. (2022) applied for their research on twitter messages posted by German gambling companies. By firstly conducting qualitative content analysis of a sample of the gathered tweets they established a framework of topics. This framework was then used for enhancing their semi-supervised topic model. Using the relatively new model CorEx, they were able to guide the algorithm by feeding the previously encountered topics into the seeds of the model (Singer et al., 2022). This second example elucidates how sequential designs can be used to improve the topic model.

Topic Modeling can also be applied in a parallel research design. Lee et al. (2019) concurrently lead qualitative interviews and conducted text mining methods including LDA topic modeling in their research on the popularity of a Korean pop band. They analyzed twitter posts and at the same time questioned fans and industry experts on the success of the musicians. By inferring topics from both the text mining and the interviews, they were able to gather insights from different perspectives (Lee et al., 2019). Our third example is yet again depicting the benefits of applying topic modeling in combination with other qualitative methods. Inferring results from the entirety of encountered topics helped the authors to get to a holistic understanding of their research area and thus producing more substantive results.

Reflecting on these examples, it seems that topic modeling can indeed augment and enhance many other methods, as well as being supported by them.

Conclusion

In this article, we provided a brief and by no means exhaustive overview on topic modeling for social scientists. We showed that the method brings about a great diversity of aspects tied to it. First, the method itself is diverse, as there are a multitude of topic modeling methods available, due to the scope of this paper we only touched briefly upon a few of them, namely LDA topic models, Top2Vec and BERTopic.

As diverse as the method are its fields of application. We showed that topic modeling can be used to benefit research in various areas of social sciences and is applicable to different kinds of unstructured text, social media posts and journal articles only being two of them. In addition to those diverse opportunities, the method also exhibits several challenges and limitations. We mentioned the problematic aspects of big data, such as incompleteness, poor accessibility, and flawed quality. Further challenges entail the language bias, as topic models are not available for many languages, especially those spoken in the global south and scientifically less funded areas. We also brought forward a challenge that we experienced ourselves learning about the method: As it requires basic programming skills, topic modeling might be disapproved of by social researchers.

Another challenging aspect we dealt with in our article was validation. However demanding, validation is crucial to the method, and furthermore to its recognition as a valid social research method.

Looking ahead, we are eager to witness the development of topic modeling in social sciences. The large amount of data that our society is generating will most likely maintain the necessity of computational methods in the social sciences. What cannot be determined yet is whether there will be more interdisciplinary cooperation in science or social researchers will be taught basic programming skills by default. We also are curious whether topic modeling will mainly be used in mixed methods designs, or more often applied as an independent method in social science.

INFOBOX: The main points of this article can also be listened to: A podcast on topic modeling for social scientists also featuring input of two experts in the field can be found at:

<https://youtu.be/xqtYvuVcVuo>

Literature

Albanese, N. C. (2022). Topic Modeling with LSA, pLSA, LDA, NMF, BERTopic, Top2Vec: a Comparison. A comparison between different topic modeling strategies including practical Python examples.

<https://towardsdatascience.com/topic-modeling-with-lsa-plsa-lda-nmf-bertopic-top2vec-a-comparison-5e6ce4b1e4a5#e768>

Baranowski, M. (2022). Epistemological aspect of topic modelling in the social sciences: Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Przełqđ Krytyczny*, 4(1), 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.14746/pk.2022.4.1.1>

Blei, D. M. (2012). Probabilistic topic models. *Communications of the ACM*, 55(4), 77-84. <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2133806.2133826>

Chen, Y., Peng, Z., Kim, S. H., & Choi, C. W. (2023). What We Can Do and Cannot Do with Topic Modeling: A Systematic Review. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19312458.2023.2167965>

Denny, M. J., & Spirling, A. (2018). Text Preprocessing For Unsupervised Learning: Why It Matters, When It Misleads, And What To Do About It. *Political Analysis*, 26(2), 168–189. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pan.2017.44>

DiMaggio, P., Nag, M., & Blei, D. (2013). Exploiting affinities between topic modeling and the sociological perspective on culture: Application to newspaper coverage of US government arts funding. *Poetics*, 41(6), 570-606. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.poetic.2013.08.004>

Edelmann, A., Wolff, T., Montagne, D., & Bail, C. A. (2020). Computational social science and sociology. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 46, 61-81. [10.1146/annurev-soc-121919-054621](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-121919-054621)

Egger, R., & Yu, J. (2022). A topic modeling comparison between lda, nmf, top2vec, and bertopic to demystify twitter posts. *Frontiers in sociology*, 7, 886498.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2022.886498>

Eickhoff, M., & Wieneke, R. (2018). Understanding topic models in context: a mixed-methods approach to the meaningful analysis of large document collections. Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences.

<https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/bitstreams/e29e4a87-9b33-4c74-ad71-bdd0e66a4455/download>

Grimmer, J., Roberts, M. E., & Stewart, B. M. (2022). *Text as data: A new framework for machine learning and the social sciences*. Princeton University Press.

Grootendorst, M. (2022). BERTopic: Neural topic modeling with a class-based TF-IDF procedure. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.05794*. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2203.05794.pdf>

Halcomb, E. J., Andrew, S., & Brannen, J. (2009). Introduction to mixed methods research for nursing and the health sciences. In: Halcomb, E. J. & Andrew, S. (Eds.) *Mixed methods research for nursing and the health sciences* (1. Ed., p. 1-12). Blackwell Publishing Ltd.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/book/10.1002/9781444316490>

Hulstaert, L. (2017). LDA2vec: Word Embeddings in Topic Models. *Towards Data Science*,

<https://towardsdatascience.com/lda2vec-word-embeddings-in-topic-models-4ee3fc4b2843>

Jacobi, C., Van Atteveldt, W., & Welbers, K. (2016). Quantitative analysis of large amounts of journalistic texts using topic modelling. *Digital Journalism*, 4(1), 89–106.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2015.1093271>

Kitchin, R. (2014). Big Data, new epistemologies and paradigm shifts. *Big data & society*, 1(1),

<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951714528481>

Lazer, D. M., Pentland, A., Watts, D. J., Aral, S., Athey, S., Contractor, N., Freelon, D., Gonzales-Bailon, S., King, G., Margetts, H., Nelson, A., Salganik, M.J., Strohmaier, M., Vespignani, A. & Wagner, C. (2020). Computational social science: Obstacles and opportunities. *Science*, 369(6507), 1060-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaz8170>

Lee, S. H., Choi, S., & Kim, H. W. (2021). Unveiling the success factors of BTS: a mixed-methods approach. *Internet Research*, 31(5), 1518-1540. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-12-2019-0507>

NamyaLG (2021). How Many Topics? Toward Data Science,
<https://namyalg.medium.com/how-many-topics-4b1095510d0e>

Patty, J. W., & Penn, E. M. (2015). Analyzing Big Data: Social Choice and Measurement. *PS: Political Science & Politics*, 48(01), 95–101. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049096514001814>

Quinn, K. M., Monroe, B. L., Colaresi, M., Crespin, M. H., & Radev, D. R. (2010). How to Analyze Political Attention with Minimal Assumptions and Costs. *American Journal of Political Science*, 54(1), 209–228. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2009.00427.x>

Salganik. (2018). *Bit by bit: social research in the digital age*. Princeton University Press.
<http://media.obvsg.at/AC14485287-1001>

Singer, J., Kufenko, V., Wöhr, A., Wuketich, M., & Otterbach, S. (2022). How do Gambling Providers Use the Social Network Twitter in Germany? An Explorative Mixed-Methods Topic Modeling Approach. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 1-28.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10899-022-10158-y>

Törnberg, P., & Törnberg, A. (2018). The limits of computation: A philosophical critique of contemporary Big Data research. *Big Data & Society*, 5(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951718811843>

Van Atteveldt, W., & Peng, T.-Q. (2018). When Communication Meets Computation: Opportunities, Challenges, and Pitfalls in Computational Communication Science. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 12(2–3), 81–92.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/19312458.2018.1458084>

Van Atteveldt, W., Trilling, D., & Calderón, C. A. (2022). *Computational Analysis of Communication*. Wiley Blackwell. Accessable via <https://cssbook.net/>

Waldherr, A., Geise, S., Mahrt, M., Katzenbach, C. & Nuernbergk, C. (2021). Toward a stronger theoretical grounding of computational communication science. *Computational Communication Research*, 3(2), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.5117/ccr2021.02.002.wald>

Zamith, R., & Lewis, S. C. (2015). Content Analysis and the Algorithmic Coder: What Computational Social Science Means for Traditional Modes of Media Analysis. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 659(1), 307–318.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716215570576>